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The Ontology of Liveness: Liveness, Disappearance and Performance in Performance Studies

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Abstract:

This paper “The Ontology of Liveness; Liveness, Disappearance and Performance in Performance Studies” aims to collect arguments given by performance scholars like *Peggy Phelan, Philip Auslander, Richard Schechner, Joseph Rosch, Suzane M. Jaeger*.

This paper will locate their arguments over the debate of live performance, reproductions, afterlife and will locate performances to probe into the debate and to validate writer’s perception. To locate theatre productions this paper will take performances of Amitesh Grover, Pickle Factory production house, and writer’s own performance experience, meanwhile this paper aims to probe into the manner of liveness and its debates.

Keywords: Liveness, Re-Production, Afterlife, Disappearance.

The liveness debate occurs through multiples scholars like *Peggy Phelan, Philip Auslander, Richard Schechner, Joseph Rosch, Suzane M. Jaeger*; this paper will locate their arguments, comment on those placed arguments from a subjective view and to locate those comments through performances I have seen or performed in. liveness in the field of performance studies is highly argumentative as in the sense of performance’s archiving aspects in order to keeps an afterlife sense of the performance occurred. But does that archive document touches the sense of liveness? is the search to address in this paper.

Peggy Phelan in her work *The Ontology of performance: Representation without Reproduction in Unmarked: The Politics of Performance* talked about the ontology of performance which lies in only 'Now', means the performance values only in now. To address her very statement she has given us various examples, as in the body which is in pain and the performer who is acting out the pain, elaboratively if the body is having a severe injury, is feeling the pain by all senses and mind itself then the performer can address the pain in space in time, cause and consequences as well but when the empathetic body is addressing the pain of someone else he or she may only be able to locate the expression of it to flourish out the acting, the person's mind who is not in pain would not be able to locate the exact feeling or sense of the body who is bearing the pain scientifically. Empathetically it can be located but that was not also the exact sense of it. Another instance drawn by *Phelan* is *Sophie Calle's* documentation of how she has photographed the galleries of Isabella Stewart Gardner Museum in Boston in which some of the paintings were stolen, *Calle* had those in photographed, then after that she asked the visitors and members to describe about those stolen pictures and she transcribed them and then added them beside the photographs. According to *Phelan*, *Calle's* work suggests another kind of performance in which archiving a piece of art can be seen as a performative expression by its transcription. *Phelan* is might suggesting that *Calle's* work is working as a continuation of the lost pictures it is holding the substitutional presence in it, in which disappearance and then re-appearance through memory is becomes a performance through subjective notion. Another example drawn by *Phelan* on *Calle's* work is her *Ghosts* piece located in Museum of Modern Art New York, where some of the paintings were on loan and *Calle* asked curators and guards about those pictures to describe them and to draw their memory about the paintings and then she arranged them together and put them on display board. This way the motif of the painting subverts through *Calle's* work because those described texts and those drawn out pictures were no more only the paintings to showcase it became another piece of art through the subjective

views who had drawn them or described them from their own experience of seeing those pictures, it is not possible to see a picture the way I see it and another person seeing it, so the subjective memory performance is indeed somewhere becoming the object under house arrest and captivated but it is not accurate neither validated.

Meanwhile, Derridean deconstruction concept also refers to the meaning which is not always fixed and language or interpretations are not exactly have a fixed notion, subjective views always differ from one person to another, I am referring deconstruction to validate that those lost paintings had a valid meaning which does not align with those documented pieces that documentation differs in terms of its meaning and essence. There is another article of *Suzane M. Jaeger's Embodiment of Presence The Ontology of presence Reconsidered* in which she quotes *Maurice Marleau Ponty's* idea on reality also refers to the quasi-same probability in which he is suggesting 'Phenomenology of Perception' what in detailed explanation what we grasp from our own perception or way of viewing a particular thing seems real to us but the reason I am adding this idea into liveness debate is to probe into the manner of real and the concept of real to individual, some people who have not seen the real pictures or paintings might locate those documentations as ultimate or a person who had encountered the real once and then the same person is also seeing the documentation might locate the essence of artistic birth and the inspired or documented piece of art. Therefore, what is livelier is also a subjective notion of experience, seeing things and perceiving things, but what has made is made for the one and one time it cannot be made again it may have a re-making of the same piece what considered as first copy or replica in general artistic market. *Jaeger* also talked about *Peter Brook* and his theatre practices as immediacy what remains his remarks as a theatre practitioner, his beliefs on actor's immediacy and spontaneity creates an immense impact in the context of an on stage performance, an actor can express the real spontaneous feeling when he is live, and it only occurs once, which is not so wrong because in the case of documentation the performer

can take several takes in order to make the shot perfect as it is scripted but on stage is the performer is forgetting his or her own dialogue that also marks as a performance in a way. Performance lies in being in the moment when it is occurring and only in that time it is live for the performer and for the audience as well.

¹The next philosopher *Philip Auslander* in his *Liveness and the Anxiety of Simulation* shared William Reports in which he talked about presence, according to him presence makes an impact, but what mediatized performance is creating it is reevaluating the essence of live

performance and degrading the value of live performance, and theatre performances are holding that space by not allowing the mediatized version and by their ability to engage people in the auditorium itself. In respect of this argument placed by

Auslander I would like to bring the example of *Amitesh Grover's* cyber play *The Last Poet* written during covid pandemic 2020, April. The very play situated fully in a cyber city shown in the pictures below, in which performers were performing from their own home through a social platform and audiences were also joining them accordingly via same source, this indeed falls under the modern form of theatre and a mediatized theatre production which does

→ **(The cyber city overview through director's lens)**

not have a definite end, and timing, audience can initially join and leave according to their own conveniences which also reminds us the forms of audiences defined by *Philip Auslander*. Ritual audience, those who are involving themselves into performances by their own will and wishes to be an active part of a performance like audiences in the play "The Last Poet". Accidental

¹ Picture downloaded from website;- https://images.squarespace-cdn.com/content/v1/5a6086f0d74cff47a5d9d983/1611325003587-C2259YDD95MF0DKJ70QW/LP_Show4.jpg?format=2500w

audience who are encountering a performance through some documentations, like from an archived performance like television.

Here actors and audiences are meeting through the cyber path, instead of their physical presence they were in their virtual presence, which might symbolize body as mind which is present in the performance as an audience, what claims another point to raise that in these theatre productions audience works as an active performer and without them the performance would not get a sense of performance as such.

Auslander made another statement which is the state of 'After life', according to him there is an afterlife of a performance what stays in spectator's memory, in respect of this I would like to quote *Joseph Rosch*'s work *Introduction: History, Memory and Performance* where *Rosch* talked about re-production, one of the example drawn was that how the memory of a dead speak through the bodies of the living likewise the performance remains in spectator's memory. It is not much controversial that what we encounter by our own eyes or what we hear directly that generates an aftereffect may be that is why we were taught to read loudly in our childhood by our parents and eventually whatever had as our syllabus by then we remember it even today, our mind recalls it whenever we need to. Our body and our mind work as a site of documentation where we document every single experience we encountered by one's own selves. *Amitesh Grover*'s another biographical work on *Habib Tanvir* probes into the manner

² Pictures downloaded from website; - <https://amiteshgrover.com/the-last-poet>

of memorizing and archiving and re-inventing titled *The Table Radica*. This very production dealt with *Habib Tanvir's* cookbook and his archived photos, of himself and his wife's as well. *Grover* used those food recipes and prepared them and used them as a stage prop to use; he also used the pictures of *Tanvir* and his wife in framed as a stage prop as seen in the pictures bellow.

The very play *Table Radica* structured with those food items *Grover* offers food to the audience as they will have the food and this is a part of the production to taste and to see those pictures given to them, they can touch those photo frames, they will interact with each other between the show which is also not a linear way in the theatre performance. In a very linear way of theatre performance audience are supposed to be the silent receiver, but here what *Grover* directing is the interaction in order to pass foods, frames. There is another interesting part of this very production is the story telling part which is narrated by *Grover* himself as the above pictures suggesting, *Grover* narrating the story to the audience in between audience as an active participant or I would say performers having their foods, interacting with each other. The context of after life is proved by the way of the production held here, audience will carry the memory of the taste, vision and the story with them which is very modern theatre as in context and concept. The audience who are the performers as well will be able to locate those taste, and vision and story in their memory and to re-call as per their needs. According to *Grover*,

³ Pictures downloaded from website; - <https://amiteshgrover.com/tableradica>

audience's active participation makes an impact to them as to memorize every single thing just the way rehearsal does to the performers, but the debate that this paper is attempting to locate is that does these instances makes really a thing live like it was when performed for the first time? Or is it just substitute of a particular project or re-making of the memory. The projection what had happened is not negotiable in any context in order to its repetition, when it is being re-make it is not the first make of the production, as in respect to *The Table Radica*, audiences/performers memory will be an after life but not the live production, or the live performance.

There is this production held on 2018, at Murshidabad Subhash Chandra Bose Centenary College, called *Natyashastra*, performed by the department of English, Bricoleurs. This very production is an improvised adaptation of Bharata Muni's *Natyashastra*, consists nine Rasa's in which we took six. They are Adbhuta (Amazement), Sringara (Erotic), Bhayanaka (Fear), krodh (Anger), Karuna (Compassion), Shant (Peace), every Rasa corresponds to a particular bhava which is expressed

Dance Choreography on *Natyashastra* by English Literary Society, BricoleursRS, 18-06-2018

by the facial expression of the actors on stage including the offstage vocal performers. The impact of on stage live performance is no doubt visible to the audience and very easy to document the gestures but the offstage performers are not physically available to archive themselves, as in the offstage

singer who were not available physically to document, but the voice is being recorded in a mode of documentation the first on stage performance of *Natyashastra*. The lack of body's presence is another kind of argument falls under the context of archiving the body, this paper is not delving into that argument. This very production was performed again in 2019 where the vocal artist is being replaced because of her unavailability, what marks as her physical absence in general but also replacing a story or a performer is also remaking the place of it which

generates the newness in the performance. The experience what I am going to place here is that those who were there in 2018 and heard me (who sung the song) performing the Begum Akhtar's piece Hamri Atariya pe was expecting me in the show in 2019, some of them told me they liked my performance in 2018, some of the audiences watched both the productions, found the other vocal performer more accurate than my performance. Which is locating another sense of live context, who has seen me performing and has seen the 2019 production they were comparing between the two and commenting according to their perception of perceiving the voice, according to the production, but who has not seen me may be seeing the 2019 production as new and not the re-production of the 2018 show, so it was a complete argumentative context to locate which one is the live and which one is the re-make of the production for individual person but it is evidently proved that what has been performed in 2018 is the one time event and it is impossible to make that liveness again, it is very much possible to re-create it but the re-creation is not the live what happened and only an one-time event. I am attaching the pictures and the YouTube link as a reference of the *Natyashastra* Production.
https://youtu.be/IrA_aHsMcRw⁴

The reproduction of *Natyashastra* of 2018 held in the 2019 is indeed capturing another essence of performance to the audience but it is unable to capture the exact performance that had done before. The representation is the mode of documentation is creating the afterlife but it is not the present life. It is being the past event which has been archived as in keeping memory or documenting a performance. The argument of liveness thus

⁴ Pictures has been taken from the uploaded files by the original Bricoleurs profile; - https://youtu.be/IrA_aHsMcRw⁴

generates the live event as it is only present in NOW, but the liveness may also occur in the reproduction but not in the documentation.

The substitution what is made by the documentation or by cherishing the moment is being a substitute, thus it is argumentative from one's own perception, but according to my observation and the implication that I have drawn in the paper is locating directly that disappearance does not holds the liveness, once it is done, it is done, we cannot do what we did just a minute before. But we can hold that essence emotionally and can recreate it in the present.

⁵I would like to bring another example by adding the theater performance done by the production house *The Pickle Factory*, titled *Shoot the cameraman*.

It was a performance what prohibited any kind of documentation from the audience. It was a musical act, not by traditional in nature and asking for audience's consciousness.

⁵ Pictures has been taken from website; - <https://picklefactory.in/programmes/2024-2025/s5-holding-space-week-1/>

<https://picklefactory.in/programmes/2024-2025/s5-holding-space/s5-india-tour/>

⁶ It advocates various performative gestures but what is more likely to be noted is that, there is this scene where somebody from the performers came into the audience's

place with a gun holding in hand pointing the stage, the whole auditorium was in red light and the scene became very fascinating yet suspicious and rigorous. The play must have been documented by the authors but I am sure that the essence we got or the sensation of fear we had is unable to document or to archive. Those who were present in that show can only have this very sensation; it is unable to recognize by seeing a documented video or by a story telling. Therefore, the liveness debate is non-negotiable in order to capture it's liveness by its disappearance. It can only be live when it is happening means only in now.

There is this continuation of the performance through the audience's memory which is considered as its afterlife but the true essence what delineates in the present moment only. The motif of this paper was to locate those arguments in support of this above statement that it is only live when it is happening and if we talk about its liveness then it occurs though the memory through the emotional space of the spectator. The ontology of liveness thus remains in the presence of the performance; liveness cannot be preserved or showcased.

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2. Amitesh Grover, The Table Radica

⁶ picture has been taken from website; - <https://picklefactory.in/programmes/2024-2025/s5-holding-space-week-1/>

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